

Influence of Organizational Culture on Organization Performance: A Case of the Seventh-Day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region

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Abstracts: This study was pursued to investigate the influence of organization culture on the performance of Seventh-day Adventists Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. The study adopted quantitative approach using descriptive survey and correlational designs. The targeted population for this study was the employees working in five (5) Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions in Kilimanjaro region. The five Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions have a total of 196 working staff, both teaching and non-teaching staffs from whom a sample of 132 staffs were sampled using simple random sampling technique. Data were collected through self-administered close ended questionnaires and the analysis of the collected data was done through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS. V.26) software and they were interpreted descriptively. The findings reported a positive and significant relationship between group culture and performance of the institutions, similar relationship was also found to exist between adhocracy culture and performance of the institutions. On the other hand, the findings reported insignificant relationship between hierarchical and market cultures and performance of these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. Such findings imply that, group and adhocracy cultures have positive and significant effect on performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions, while hierarchical and market organization cultures have no significant effect on the performance of these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions. The study recommends for adoptions of group and adhocracy organization cultures as they positively contribute to the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions. The study further recommended for dropping out hierarchical and market organization cultures since they have no significant effect on the performance of these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions.

Keywords: Organization Culture, Organization Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The sustainable development of any organization is closely related to the type of culture of that organization (Agwo, 2014). Tianya (2015) contends that, during the establishment and development of any organization a specific kind of organizational culture eventually appears. Tianya (2015) further states that, the purpose of organizational culture is to improve solidarity and cohesion, and to stimulate employees' enthusiasm and creativity to improve the organization's economic efficiency.

Worldwide, a number of studies have linked the organization culture with the performance of the organization (Luiza & Tiru, 2021; Jardon & Martinez-Cobas, 2019; Reisman, 2016). For example, Ahmed and Shafiq, (2014) from Pakistan conducted a study that sought to determine the impact of organizational culture on organizational performance in order to know that how culture of an organization assist in enhancing the organizational performance. Their findings showed that,

organizational culture plays an important role in achieving the organizational objective. Result show that there is high uncertainty avoidance in the organization, higher the uncertainty avoidance better will be organizational performance. In East Africa, Owino and Kibera, (2019) conducted a study that aimed at determining the influence of organizational culture on the performance of microfinance institutions in Kenya, and the study established that organizational culture has a significant influence on institutions performance.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite all the strong evidence on the role of organization culture in enhancing organization performance (Luiza & Tiru, 2021; Jardon & Martinez-Cobas, 2019; Owino & Kibera, 2019; Reisyhan, 2016; Ahmned & Shafiq 2014) yet less has been revealed concerning the effects of organization culture on the performance of the education institutions, particularly in Seventh-day Adventist educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro, Tanzania.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Generally, this study intended to investigate the influence of organization culture on the performance of Educational Institutions owned and managed by the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Kilimanjaro Region.

Specifically, this study intended;

1. To examine the type of organization culture of the Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions in Kilimanjaro.
2. To examine the perceptions of the staffs on the performance of Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions in Kilimanjaro.
3. To examine the relationship between the organization culture and the performance of Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions in Kilimanjaro

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Exploration

The Concept of Organization Culture: Organizational culture is the pattern of values, norms, beliefs, attitudes and assumptions that may not have been articulated but shape the ways in which people in organizations behave and things get done (Givens, 2014). Organization culture is defined as the set of values, beliefs, attitudes, expectations, understandings, norms shared by members of organization (O'Donnell & Boyle, 2012). It is passed from one generation of employees to the next, and determined the norms for appropriate behavior within the organization (Weber & Tarba, 2015). On the other hand, Simoneaux and Stroud, (2014) refers the culture of an organization to as the unique configuration of norms, values, beliefs and ways of behaving that characterize the manner in which groups and individuals combine to get things done. The definitions emphasizes that organizational culture is concerned with the subjective aspect of what goes on in organizations. It refers to abstractions such as values and norms that pervade the whole or part of a business, which may not be defined, discussed or even noticed. Nevertheless, culture can have a significant influence on people's behaviour. (Viegas-Pires, 2013). Organizational culture is an important source of sustained competitive advantage as it possesses the characteristics of a strategic asset, namely scarcity, inimitability, value creating and non-trade ability (Scheider, Ehrhat, & Macey, 2013).

The Concept of Organization Performance: Organizational performance on the other hand refers to the degree to which the organization, with some informational, financial, and human resources, positions itself effectively on the business market (Gabriela, 2020). According to Market Business News, organizational performance comprises real results or outputs compared with intended outputs. The analysis focuses on three main outcomes, namely, shareholder value performance; financial performance; and market performance. Shareholder value performance looks at how much a company enriches its shareholders, financial performance refers to measuring a company's operations and policies in monetary terms and market performance measures how well a company or product performs in the marketplace. Nur, Zulkiffliya, and Perera, (2011), defines organization performance as the operational ability to satisfy the desires of the business's major shareholders and it must be assessed to measure business accomplishment.

Theoretical Framework

This study was built upon the Competing Value Framework. In the early 1980s, organizational researchers developed the Competing Value Framework as a conceptual framework to integrate criteria of organizational "effectiveness" (Wiewiora

et al., 2012). The framework is a synthesis of organizational theories, and posits that most organizations can be characterized along two dimensions, each representing alternative approaches to basic challenges that all organizations must resolve in order to function. According to Helfrich, Li, Mohr, and Meterko (2007), the first set of competing values is the degree to which an organization emphasizes centralization and control over organizational processes versus decentralization and flexibility. The second set of competing values is the degree to which the organization is oriented toward its own internal environment and processes versus the external environment and relationships with outside entities, such as regulators, suppliers, competitors, partners and customers. Cross-classifying organizations on these two values dimensions results in four archetypes, referred to as hierarchical, rational, entrepreneurial, and team cultures.

The Competing Value Framework is applicable in this study as it best explains the characteristics of individual type of organization culture and thus the understanding of the characteristics will enable the researcher to clearly assess the type of organization culture applied in the Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions and also to assess the examine the impact of applied organization culture on the performance of Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions.

Empirical Studies

The topic of organization culture has become of great importance among the Investors and managers of various organizations. Most of them seeking to know how organization culture of a particular organization can affect the performance of that particular organization. This section brings summary of previous studies that were done by various scholars on the types of organization culture practiced by different organizations as well as the studies on relationship between organization culture and the organization performance.

Types of Organization Culture Practiced by Organizations

In their study, Luiza and Tiru (n.d) aimed to document the specific organizational culture existing in the General Directorate for Social Work and Child Protection (DGASPC) in the Gorj County, Romania. Study included 286 participants that hold various positions at DGASPC Gorj (social workers, psychologists, and educators). The chosen investigative instrument is the organizational culture assessment instrument (OCAI), a questionnaire designed to interpret organizational phenomena, developed by Cameron and Quinn and based on the conceptual framework of the “competing values framework”. The study identified four types of culture (group culture, adhocracy culture, hierarchy culture, and market culture) and the tool allows an analysis of organizational culture based on the employees’ perception of the existing culture as well as also on their preferences regarding the way they would like to change the organizational culture in the future. The results show that the dominant culture was the hierarchy culture, closely followed by elements of group culture.

Ahmed and Shafiq (2014) conducted a study in Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The purpose of their study was to determine the impact of organizational culture on organizational performance in order to know that how culture of an organization assist in enhancing the organizational performance. Balance score card was used to measure the organizational performance. Quantitative approach was adopted in which a questionnaire was used to collect the data. 22 questionnaires were distributed to the research participants out of which 15 questionnaires were returned to the researchers with complete information. The findings indicated that all the dimension of the organization culture were practiced and they influenced different perspective of organizational performance.

Owino and Kibera, (2019) conducted a study that aimed at determining the influence of organizational culture on the performance of microfinance institutions in Kenya. A descriptive cross-sectional survey design was adopted. Secondary data were collected from annual reports by the Association of Microfinance Institutions in Kenya and the Microfinance Rating Africa. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaire targeting the chief executive officer, human resource manager, and marketing manager. Data were analyzed using factor analysis and hierarchical regression. Their analysis identified clan and hierarchy as the dominant cultural typologies in the microfinance industry.

Relationship between Organization Culture and the Organization Performance

In 2014, Yzida conducted a study in Turkey. The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between the dimensions of organizational culture (power distance, uncertainty avoidance etc. and corporate entrepreneurship and the effects of organizational culture on corporate entrepreneurship. The survey was conducted on a leading multinational company in Turkey. Analyses results showed that power distance, one of the organizational culture factors, has positive

effects on corporate entrepreneurship innovativeness dimension. In addition masculinity has negative effects on new business venturing. This study showed the strategic importance of organizational culture by presenting evidence of the relationship between cultural dimensions and corporate entrepreneurship.

Akhatr, et al, (2016) in London examined the effect of an entrepreneurial culture on an employee's innovation output, and explores three mechanisms by which this may be achieved. In a sample of 523 working adults, the relationship between entrepreneurial culture and innovation output was fully mediated by work engagement. Furthermore, it was reported that entrepreneurial culture positively moderated the relationship between an individual's entrepreneurial personality and innovation output.

A study by Dzomonda and Fatoki, (2019) aimed at investigating the impact of organizational culture on the entrepreneurial orientation of SMEs in South Africa. A quantitative research method was used and 103 SMEs participated in the survey. The random sampling technique was used. Self-administered questionnaires were utilized to collect data in a survey. A sample of 89 SME owner/managers participated in the survey. Data analysis included descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and regression analysis. The results indicated that SMEs display average levels of entrepreneurial orientation and average levels of organizational culture. Furthermore, the results showed a significant positive relationship between organizational culture and entrepreneurial orientation of SMEs.

Number of studies have been carried out concerning the topic of organization culture and its impact, influence and relationship with firms, company's or institution's performance. For instance, Jardon and Martinez-Cobas, (2019) studied the relationship between organization culture and organization performance, while Pathirana, (2019) and Luiza and Tiru (n.d) studied the dimensions and types of organization culture in firms. On the other hand, Tang, Park, Agarwal, and Liu, (2020), Akhatr, et al (2016), Ahmed and Shafiq, (2014), Dzomonda and Fatoki, (2019) and Owino and Kibera, (2019) focused on studying the impacts and influence that organization culture has on performance of the organizations or institutions.

These studies have reported that culture of an organization has direct impacts on performance of an organization (Dzomonda & Fatoki, 2019; and Tang, Park, Agarwal, and Liu, (2020) and also, there is an existing relationship between organization culture and performance of the employee in the organization (Jardon & Martinez-Cobas, 2019). However, much are to be explored on how an Organization Culture can affect the performance of the non-profit organization particularly, the performance of Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions . Thus, this study was conducted to bridge the gap on the influence of Organization Culture on the performance of Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed quantitative research approach using descriptive survey and correlational research designs as explained by McCombes (2019) and Bhandari (2021) respectively. The targeted population of this study were the staffs working in five Seventh-day Adventist education institutions located in Kilimanjaro Region. Simple random sampling was used to sample 132 staffs from the population of 196 staffs.

Primary data were collected using self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was preferred because they are not only easy to distribute to a larger sample but also, they guarantee anonymity of respondents and reduce researcher's bias on data (Kothari, 2004). Data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0 the demographic data were analyzed on descriptively by using frequencies and percentage table.

For research questions one and two which examined the types of organization culture of the Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions and examined the perceptions of the staffs on the performance of Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions in Kilimanjaro respectively were analyzed by using descriptive statistics in terms of mean scores, whereby mean scores were interpreted under the following criteria of five-point scale: 1.00-1.49 = Strongly Disagree, 1.50-2.49 = Disagree, 2.50-3.49= Neutral, 3.50-4.49 = Agree and 4.50-5.00 = Strongly Agree.

The hypothesis of the study which assumes no significant relationship between organization cultures and the performance of Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions was tested by inferential statistics namely Pearson product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Nature of existing correlation would be either positive or negative and was interpreted under the following criteria: $\geq .70$ = strong relationship, $\geq .50$ = moderate relationship and $\leq .50$ = weak relationship.

4. FINDINGS

Descriptive Analysis on the Types of Organization Culture in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro.

The first research question sought to identify the types of organization culture practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist educational institutions located in Kilimanjaro region. This was done through assessing unique features of the four types of organization culture (Group culture, Hierarchical Culture, Adhocracy Culture and Market Culture) to see if they are being practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institution in Kilimanjaro region.

4.1 Group Culture

Table 1: Group Culture

Questionnaire Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Mangers in my institution are warm and caring. They seek to develop employees' full potential and act as their mentors or guides	132	1	5	2.62	1.074
The glue that holds my institution together is loyalty and tradition. Commitment to this institution runs high.	130	2	5	3.93	.559
In my institution, new or other important information reaches employees in due time	130	2	5	4.12	.618
My Institution emphasizes human resources. High cohesion and morale in the organization are important	130	2	5	4.03	.634
In my institution, employees always agree about most important things, when solving questions, problems or conflicts	130	1	5	3.76	.824

Source: Field Data (2022)

Table 1 above presents that, with a mean score of 2.62 and standard deviation of 1.074, the respondents were neutral on if Mangers in their institution are warm and caring and if they seek to develop employees' full potential and act as their mentors or guides. Such findings imply that, the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are not sure if the group culture is being practiced in their working place. These findings are contradicting with the argument of Jardon and Martinez-Cobas, (2019) who insisted that, for group culture to be successfully practiced within an organization, the manager and leaders are to develop employees' full potential and act as their mentors or guides.

The findings further report that, with a mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of .559, the respondents agreed that, the glue that holds their institution together was loyalty and tradition, and also commitment to their institutions was running high. Such findings suggest that, the employees in the in the Seventh-day Adventist Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are loyal to their institutions and they are committed to their institutions. Based on these findings, it can be said that, through loyalty and commitment to their institutions, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are practicing the group culture. These findings are supported by the argument of Heinz, (2022) who mentions loyalty to the organization and commitment of the employees as the aspects of the Group culture.

Also, the findings showed that, with a mean score of 4.12 and standard deviation of .618, the repondents of the questionnaire agreed that, in their institutions, new or other important information reaches employees in due time. This implies that, the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are communicated on time and thus they have access to information regarding their institutions. Through such communication within the institutions, it can be suggested that, the Seventh-day Adventists Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro are practicing group culture. This argument can be supported by Heinz, (2022) who contends that, in group culture every individual is valued and communication is a top priority.

Cohesion among the employee was another aspect investigated as an aspect of group culture. The findings show that, with the mean score of 4.03 and standard deviation of .634 the respondents agreed that, their institutions emphasize human resources while high cohesion and morale in the institutions are important. These findings suggests that, there is strong cohesion and morale among the employees of the institutions, implying presence of group culture in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions. This argument is supported by Heinz, (2022) who contended that, in group culture, employees are connected together as family.

It was also reported that, with the mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation of .824, the respondents agreed that, in their institutions, employees always agree about most important things, when solving questions, problems or conflicts. This implies that, problem solving and decision making in these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions are done inclusively. Inclusion of employees in discussion of important things, and when solving questions, problems or conflicts has been mentioned as one of the characteristics of the group culture by Akhatr, et al, (2016).

Despite the fact that, the respondents were neutral on if managers in their institutions are warm and caring and if they seek to develop employees' full potential and act as their mentors or guides, yet the findings suggest that, with four of the questionnaire statements scoring a mean score between 3.50- and 4.49 implied that, Group culture as a type of Organization culture is being practiced in the Seventh-day Adventists Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. The general findings on group culture in this study are similar to those of Dzomonda and Fatoki, (2019) who also reported group culture being practised by the Small and Medium Enterprises in South Africa.

4.2 Hierarchical Culture

Table 2: Hierarchical Culture

Questionnaire Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
My institution is a very formalized and structured place. Bureaucratic procedures generally govern what people do	130	1	5	3.42	1.048
In my institution, existing rules and norms are more directive (i.e. show direction) than restrictive	132	1	5	3.80	.928
Managers in my institution are rule-enforcers. They expect employees to follow established rules, policies, and procedures	130	1	4	2.37	.908
The glue that holds my institution together is formal rules and policies. People feel that following the rules is important	132	1	5	3.17	1.299
My institution emphasizes permanence and stability. Keeping things, the same is important	132	1	5	3.85	.682

Source: Field Data (2022)

As indicated in Table 2 above, with the mean score of 3.42 and standard deviation of 1.048, the respondents agreed that, their institutions are very formalized and structured places and bureaucratic procedures generally govern what people do. Formal and structured rules being identified as features in Hierarchical Culture by Pathiranaage, (2019) makes the findings of this questionnaire statement suggest that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro are practicing the Hierarchical Culture.

Also, it was reported that, with a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation of .928 the respondents agreed that, in their institutions, existing rules and norms are more directive (i.e. show direction) than restrictive. This implies that, in these institutions, the rules set and norms are meant to direct the employees on how to get things done rather than restricting them. This is one of the features of the Hierarchical Culture as identified by Hofstede, et al, (2012). Thus existence of directive rules and norms in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions implies existence of Hierarchical Culture in these institutions.

The findings also show that, with a mean score of 2.37 and standard deviation of .908, the respondents disagreed that, the managers in their institutions are rule-enforcers, expecting the employees to follow established rules, policies, and procedures. Being neutral implies that, the employees were not sure with how their managers are enforcing the rules. Maybe the managers have not shown their standings in enforcing the rules. This is contrary to the suggestions of Heinz, (2022) who suggested that, in Hierarchical Culture, the managers and leaders are rule-enforcers, and they expect the employees to follow established rules, policies, and procedures.

It was also indicated that, with a mean score of 3.17 and standard deviation of 1.299, the respondents were neutral on whether their institutions were held together by formal rules and policies as the glue. This implies that, the employees are not fully aware of how their managers emphasize the strict adherence to the rules and policies, something that limits the full application of hierarchical culture as suggested by Hofstede, et al, (2012) that, in hierarchical culture, the glue that holds institution together is formal rules and policies and that, People (employees) feel that following the rules is important.

An emphasis on permanence and stability was another indicator of hierarchical culture that was investigated by the survey questionnaire. The findings on this indicator show that, with a mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of .682, the respondents agreed that, their institutions emphasized permanence and stability while keeping things the same was important. Such agreement suggests that, hierarchical culture is being practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro as argued by Ghinea, (2016) that, organizations with hierarchical culture emphasize permanence and stability while keeping things done the same.

With the findings showing disagreement of the employees on the managers in their institutions being rule-enforcers, expecting the employees to follow established rules, policies, and procedures; and being neutral on whether their institutions were held together by formal rules and polices as the glue, and at the same time employees being in agreement that, their institutions are very formalized and structured places, existing rules and norms are more directive than restrictive and that their institutions emphasize permanence and stability while keeping things the same, the general findings on practice of hierachical culture suggest that, hierachical culture is being practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro, however it is not the dominant culture. These findings are in harmony with those of Ahmed and Shafiq, (2014) who reported the presence of hierachical culture in the investigated telecom companies in Bahawalpur, Pakistan, however the hierarchical culture was not the dominant culture.

4.3 Adhocracy Culture

Table 3: Adhocracy Culture

Questionnaire Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
My institution is a very dynamic and entrepreneurial place. People are willing to stick their necks out and take risks.	132	1	5	3.80	.798
In my institution, employees teach each other, share skills and knowledge	132	1	5	3.95	.823
Mangers in my institution are risk-takers. They encourage employees to take risks and be innovative	132	1	5	3.90	.964
The glue that holds my institution together is commitment to innovation and development. There is an emphasis on being first.	132	2	5	4.27	.655
My institution emphasizes growth and acquiring new resources. Readiness to meet new challenges is important	132	1	5	4.09	.851

Source: Field Data (2022)

Among the features of the organizations/institutions which adopt adhocracy culture is risk taking among the employees (Meade, 2021). For the purpose of understanding if the Seventh-day Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region do practice Adhocracy culture, the questionnaire for this study investigated if the employees in the Seventh-day Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region are risk takers. With a mean score of 3.80 and standard deviation of .798, the respondents agreed that, their institutions are very dynamic and entrepreneurial places, and people are willing to stick their necks out and take risks. The audacity of taking risk among the employees suggests that, the Seventh-day Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region do practice adhocracy culture.

Knowledge sharing was another feature of adhocracy culture investigated in this study. The findings indicate that, with a mean score of 3.95 and standard deviation of .823, the respondents agreed to the questionnaire statement "In my institution, employees teach each other, share skills and knowledge". This implies that, the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions do share knowledge among themselves and hence it is suggested that, these institutions do practice adhocracy culture. These arguments are supported by Mardiana and Tjakratmadja, (2016) who contends knowledge sharing among the employees as a major feature of the adhocracy culture adopting companies.

The findings also indicate that, with a mean score of 3.90 and standard deviation of .964, the respondents agreed that, Mangers in their institution are risk-takers and that, they encourage employees to take risks and be innovative. Being risk taker is one thing, and being influenced to take risk is another. An employee may not be a risk taker in nature, but working with a risk-taking manager may influence an employee to become a risk taker. Encouraging employees to become risk taker is a feature for a manager who practice adhocracy culture (Agwo, 2014). With the findings of this study showing that, managers in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions encouraging the employees to become risk takers, it can be suggested that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro are practicing adhocracy culture.

Innovation and doing things first are mentioned to be among the characteristics in adhocracy organization culture (Meade, 2021; Heinz, 2022). In this study, with a mean score of 4.27 and Standard deviation of .655, the respondents agreed with the questionnaire statement “*The glue that holds my institution together is commitment to innovation and development and there is an emphasis on being first*”. Such agreement indicates that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are innovative and they do like to do things first, thus qualifying to be termed as adhocracy culture institutions.

The findings further indicate that, with a mean score of 4.09 and standard deviation of .851 the respondents agreed with the questionnaire statement “*My institution emphasizes growth and acquiring new resources. Readiness to meet new challenges is important*”. This signifies that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are focusing on growth and acquiring new resource while being ready to face challenges. This is also mentioned to be among the features of adhocracy culture organization by Mardiana and Tjakratmadja, (2016). Therefore though focusing on growth and acquiring new resource while being ready to face challenges, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region can be regarded as practicing adhocracy organization culture.

With all the questionnaire statements for adhocracy culture scoring the mean scores between 3.50- and 4.49, the implication is that, the respondents agreed with all the five questionnaire statements which means the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are practicing adhocracy organization culture. These findings are in line with those of Floriana and Tiru, (2021) who also reported adhocracy culture being practiced by the social work institutions in Romania.

4.4 Market Culture

Table 4: Market Culture

Questionnaire Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Managers in my institution are coordinators and coaches. They help employees meet the institution's goals and objectives	130	1	5	3.69	.922
In my institution, employees are required to meet their deadline in due	130	2	5	3.96	.589
My institution emphasizes competitive actions and achievement. Measurable goals are important	130	1	5	3.71	.839
In my institution, managers care about welfare of employees	128	2	5	3.98	.452
I get rewarded based on my accomplishment	130	1	5	3.82	.653

Source: Field Data (2022)

Meade, (2021) argues that, in the companies practising market organization culture managers help their employees meet the organizations' goals and objective through corrdinating and coaching. Based on this argument, this study investigated the practice of market culture among the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro through assessing if the managers in these institutions are helping the employees to meet the institutions' goals. The findings show that, with a mean score of 3.69 and standard deviation of .922, the repondents who were the employees of these institutions agreed that, the managers in their institutions are coordinantors and coaches, and they help the employees to meet the organizations' goals and objective. Such findings agree with the arguments of Meade (2021) and thus, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region can be regarded as practicing market organization culture.

Also the findings in Table 4.5 above indicate that, with the mean score of 3.96 and standard deviation of .589 the respondents agreed with the questionnaire statement “In my institution, employees are required to meet their deadline in due”. Such agreement implies that, the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region are assigned with works and they are being required to submit them in due time thus making these institutions qualifying to be market organization culture institutions.

Competition is another feature of market organization culture as suggested by Akhatr, et al, (2016). The findings of this study regarding competition in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region show that, with a mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation of .839 the respondents agreed that, their institution emphasize competitive actions and achievement, and that measurable goals are important. With such agreement, it can be regarded that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region are practicing market organization culture, considering the argument given by Akhatr, et al, (2016).

Jardon and Martinez-Cobas, (2019) contends that, in market organization culture, leaders have the tendencies of caring about the welfare of their subordinates as a way of motivating them to perform better. The findings in this study indicate that, with an average score of 3.98 and standard deviation of .452, the respondents who are the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region agreed that, managers in their institutions care about welfare of employees. This implies that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region do practice market organization culture.

The study also investigated the basis for rewards to the employees as one of the features in market culture. According to Agwo, (2014), the companies and organizations which apply market organization culture do reward their employees based on their accomplishment. In this study, the findings indicate that, with a mean score of 3.82 and standard deviation of .653, the respondents agreed with a statement “*I get rewarded based on my accomplishment*”. This implies that, the employees with great accomplishment are greatly rewarded and vice versa is true. Based on these findings, considering the argument of Agwo (2014), it can be suggested that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are practicing the market organization culture.

With all the questionnaire statements for market culture scoring the mean scores between 3.50- and 4.49, the implication is that, the respondents agreed with all the five questionnaire statements which means the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are practicing market organization culture. These findings are in line with those of Floriana and Tiru, (2021) who also reported adhocracy culture being practiced by the social work institutions in Romania.

4.5 Institutions' Performance

The second research question for this study sought to examine the perceptions of the staffs on the performance of Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro. Table 4.6 below presents the findings obtained after the analysis of the questionnaire statements regarding the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region.

Table 5: Performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions

Questionnaire Statements	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our leaders at conference level are satisfied with our current operational performance	132	2	5	3.98	.878
The quality of our service meets the expectations of our customers	132	1	5	3.57	1.120
We retain existing clients and manage to attract new ones	132	1	5	3.53	1.108
Reputation of our Institution in the eyes of our customers is satisfactory	132	1	5	4.03	.634
We deal with customers' complaints as fast as possible	132	2	5	3.95	.750

Source: Field Data (2022)

As indicated in Table 5 above, with a mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of .878, the respondents agreed that, their leaders at the conference level were satisfied with their current operational performance. This implies that, these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region are performing well and the leaders at conference level are satisfied with the performance of the institutions.

The findings also show that, with a mean score of 3.57 and standard deviation of 1.120, the respondents agreed that, the quality of the services offered by their institutions meets the expectations of their customers. The findings suggest that, the institutions are offering quality services and the customers are satisfied with these services.

Ability to retain the existing customers while managing to increase new customer is one of the aspect of institutions performance as suggested by Zimmerman, (2018). The finding of this study indicate that, with a mean score of 3.53 and standard deviation of 1.108, the respondents who were the employees in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region agreed that, their institution are able to retain their customers and they are able to attract new ones. Based on the argument of Zimmerman, (2018) who contends, a company or an institution which is capable of attracting, making new customers while maintaining the current ones is considered as performing institution. Therefore, since the employees of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region agreed that they are able to maintain current customers while making new ones, these institutions are regarded as well performing.

Reputation of the company/institution in the eyes of the customers is another important aspect of institution's performance. An institution with a good reputation gets the goodwill of its customers easily and hence it is termed as performing one (Ameisen, 2014). In this study, among other aspects that were used to assess the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region, there was a questionnaire statement that sought to understand the perceptions of the employees on the reputation of the institutions in the eyes of the customers. The findings showed that, with a mean score of 4.03 and standard deviation of .634, the respondents agreed that, the reputation of their institutions in the eyes of our customers is satisfactory. Considering the arguments of Ameisen, (2014), it can be suggested that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro region are performing well.

Attending and dealing with customers' complaints on time has been mentioned as non-financial aspect of institutions' performance addressed in this study. The findings on this aspect show that, with a mean score of 3.95 and standard deviation of .750, the respondents also agreed that, in their institutions, they deal with customers' complaints as fast as possible. Based on the arguments of Osawe, (2017) who argued the performing organization to be those which are able to deal with the complaints of their customers and solve them while preventing the mistakes to avoid the repetitions of the complaints from their customer, these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region can be considered as performing institutions.

The general findings regarding the perceptions of the employees on the performance of the of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region suggest that, these institutions are performing well. This is due to the fact that, all of the five questionnaire statements which were constructed to investigate the performance of the of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region scored the mean scores of between 3.50 and 4.49 implying that, the respondents agreed that, they are performing well and the leaders at conference level are satisfied with the performance of the institutions, the quality of the services offered by their institutions meets the expectations of their customers, their institution are able to retain their customers and they are able to attract new ones, the reputation of their institutions in the eyes of our customers is satisfactory and they deal with customers' complaints as fast as possible. These being non-financial aspects of institution performance, it can be suggested that, the performance of these Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region is good. These findings are in harmony with those of Floriana and Tiru, (2021) who also used non-financial aspects to establish the performance of the social works institution in Romania and reported the performance of the investigated institutions to be satisfactory.

4.6. Relationship between the Organization Culture and Social Educational Institutions Performance.

The third research question of this study was to examine the relationship between the organization culture and the performance of Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. To obtain the answers for this research question, correlation analysis using inferential statistics namely Pearson product Moment Correlation Coefficient was conducted to investigate the direction and strength of the relationship between four types of organization culture and the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. The relationship of each organization culture on performance of the institutions was tested independently.

4.6.1 Relationship between Group Culture and Institutions' Performance.

Table 6.1: Correlation between Group Culture and Institutions' Performance

Variables	Group Culture	Institutions' Performance
Group Culture	1	
Institutions' Performance	.208**	1

Source: Field Data (2022)

As indicated in Table 6.1 above, group culture correlates with performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions performance at Pearson ($R=.208$, $P=.008$) such findings imply a positive, however weak relationship between group culture and the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions performance, considering the used scale. These findings can be interpreted as that, group culture practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions positively, however slightly and significantly affect their performance. These findings are in compliance with those of Dzomonda and Fatoki, (2019) who also found group culture to have a positive relationship with performance of the SMEs in South Africa.

4.6.2 Relationship between Hierarchical Culture and Institutions' Performance

Table 6.2: Correlation between Hierarchical Culture and Institutions' Performance

	Hierarchical Culture	Institutions' Performance
Hierarchical Culture	1	
Institutions' Performance	.018	1

Source: Field Data (2022)

Table 6.2 above shows a weak and insignificant relationship between Hierarchical Culture and the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions performance at Pearson ($P=.018$; $R=.421$), this implies that, Hierarchical Culture has no significant effect on the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro. These findings are somehow in conflict with those of Ahmed and Shafiq, (2014) who reported the presence of hierarchical culture in the investigated telecom companies in Bahawalpur, Pakistan and hierarchical culture had significant influence on performance of the telecom companies.

4.6.3 Relationship between Adhocracy Culture and Institutions' Performance

Table 6.3: Correlation between Adhocracy Culture and Institutions' Performance

	Adhocracy Culture	Institutions' Performance
Adhocracy Culture	1	
Institutions' Performance	.315**	1

Source: Field Data (2022)

Table 6.3 above indicates that, Adhocracy culture correlates with Institutions' performance at Pearson ($P=.315$, $R=.000$). Such findings suggest that, there is a positive and yet weak relationship between adhocracy culture and the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. Such relationship can be interpreted as that, the adhocracy culture applied has a slight effect on the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region and such effect is significant. These findings are in harmony with those of Floriana and Tiru, (2021) who also reported adhocracy culture to have significant relationship with the performance of the social work institutions in Romania.

4.6.4 Relationship between Market Culture and Institutions' Performance.

Table 6.4: Correlation between Market Culture and Institutions' Performance

	Adhocracy Culture	Institutions' Performance
Adhocracy Culture	1	
Institutions' Performance	.315**	1

Source: Field Data (2022)

As presented in Table 6.4 above, market culture correlates with the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions at Pearson ($P=.067$, $R=.224$) which implies a weak and insignificant relationship between market culture and the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. In other words, it can be said that, market culture that is practiced in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions has no significant effect on the performance of the institutions. These findings are in controve with those of Akhatr, et al, (2016) who reported that market culture positively moderated the relationship between an individual's entrepreneurial personality and innovation output.

Generally, the findings of this study call for both acceptance as well as rejection of the hypothesis of the study. On one side, basing of group and adhocracy cultures, the findings call for rejection of the study hypothesis which assumed there is no significant relationship between organization culture and performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro. On the other hand, focusing of Hierarchical Culture and Market Culture, the findings of the study call for acceptance of the hypothesis of the study.

5. CONCLUSION

In line with the findings, this study concludes that, the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region are practicing all of the four types of the Organization culture. In line with these findings the study concludes that, practicing group culture and adhocracy culture in the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region have significant influence on the performance of the institutions. Therefore, to keep on performing well, the managers should strengthen group culture in their organizations through being warm and caring and as they seek to develop employees' full potential and act as their mentors or guides, they should strengthen/establish a strong communication channel so that, the employee can communicate on time and thus they have access to information regarding their institutions as well as emphasizing on human resources cohesion and morale in the organization. Also, the study concludes that, for the managers to strengthen the performance of their organizations, they should consider strengthening adhocracy culture in their organization through emphasizing the audacity of taking risk among the employees, knowledge sharing among the employees as well as emphasizing growth and acquisition of new resources among the employees.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher presents the following recommendations to the management of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region.

The management of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region should adopt group and adhocracy culture which have been proven to have positive and significant effect on performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions .

By using quantitative study which is limited numerical findings; this study reported insignificant influence of the hierarchical and market organization cultures on performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region, the researcher calls for qualitative study to investigate why hierarchical and market organization cultures have insignificant influence on the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region. A qualitative study will provide in-depth explanations to why hierarchical organization culture and market organization culture have insignificant influence on the performance of the Seventh-day Adventist Educational Institutions in Kilimanjaro Region.

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